

Analysis of the Marketing Strategies of Reliance Industries (Petroleum & Oil Company) In Enhancing Its Petroleum Business & Establishing as A Global-Level Petroleum Company

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Abstract -Reliance Petroleum's focus is on driving the country towards development with its progressed items and administrations comprising of High-Speed Diesel, Petrol, Auto LPG, Greases, Aviation Fuel, Pressed LPG catering to diverse sections extending from two-wheelers to aircraft fuelling & farm gear to overwhelming building vehicles. With a deliberately extended network of 1380+ retail outlets spread over the nation, Reliance Petroleum's fuel retail trade gives esteem to its clients through a 100% automatic network, backed by current innovation. In 2018, Reliance Petroleum was the primary Indian company to outperform Rupees eight hundred thousand crores (US\$ 122.85 billion) in market capitalization and crosses the three hundred million client mark. Reliance crude oil, once place next with various corporations, spends lesser on promotions associate degree advertisements, however, Reliance Petroleum believes in reducing prices to attract its customers. It sticks to majorly of Below-the-line advertising as compared to Above-the-Line advertising as its costs less to the company or its retail sector's new launch product to make an initial buzz among the purchasers. Reliance petroleum follows best processes and automation systems, uniformly and systematically, whereas delivering High-Speed Diesel, Petrol, motorcar LPG and Lubricants from its fuel stations across the country. Reliance Industries has emerged as the most important wealth creator over 2014-19, consistent with Motilal Oswal's twenty-fourth Annual Wealth Creation Study 2019. The Rs 5.6 hundred thousand crore wealth created by Reliance is that the highest ever far by an enormous margin.

Key Words:Market capitalization, petroleum, diesel, fuel, retail outlets, promotions

1. INTRODUCTION

The main threat of the corporation is that its existing competitors within the current market. The economic depression that the globe two-faced throughout the past few years has affected greatly within the business. Tata is one of Reliance Industries Limited (RIL)'s prime competitors. Tata was founded in 1868 in Bombay, Maharashtra. Tata operates within the Business Support Services business. Tata generates \$29.4B above revenue than Reliance Industries Limited (RIL). Adani may be a high challenger of Reliance Industries Limited (RIL). Adani was founded in 1988 and is headquartered in Ahmedabad, Gujarat. Adani is within the Business Support Services business. Adani generates \$68.3B less revenue vs. Reliance Industries Limited (RIL). Their business is principally targeted in the Asian nations by concerning eighth.

Along with all these corporates, the retail promoting of crude oil product in India is mostly by the public Sector Oil marketing companies (OMCs) i.e., Indian Oil Corporation Limited, Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited, Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited, Mangalore Refinery & Petrochemicals Limited, Bharat Oman Refineries Limited. It appears like Reliance Industries Limited didn't establish its business worldwide, because for each business international market may be an excellent chance to extend their processing.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

As in line with the current researches of Motilal Oswal Securities, Reliance Industries Limited's stock prices have nearly tripled over the past five years, outperforming the Nifty through 122% on a cumulative basis. This has been driven by the strengthening of the refining and petrochemical companies of Reliance Industries Limited and there may be additionally some giant build-up in its retail and telecom segments. Moreover, we assume the core business to face headwinds in 2019. While telecom and retail continue to be in a widespread build-up mode.

The reviews additionally stated that because of the addition in the refining potential of 2.6mbopd in 2019, much ahead of demand increase of 1.1mbopd. While the sales have been developing at an impressive pace (~2x in 9MFY19), the contribution from petrochemical maintains margins for the retail low at 4.6%. While this combined with excessive product inventories, is likely to result in subdued GRMs in FY20. And the expansions in the US/China are possible to bring about the whole incremental petrochemical capacity of 7mmtpa in 2019 itself, more than the 6mmtpa delivered in 2017/18.

Global refining and petrochemical are buying and selling at ~6x FY20 EV/EBITDA. Motilal Oswal Securities value Reliance Industries Limited's refining and petrochemical segments at 7.5x – the top class here displays the company's superior capability to control the crude basket, refinery yields, hedging and a couple of feedstocks for its petrochemical segment.

3. METHODOLOGY

As per the prerequisites of the destinations of the expressed study the Research plan is utilized for the pondering of the descriptive sorting. For this reason, the accessible auxiliary information was all together and broadly used for the research purpose. The more prominent level of precision in considering the accessible assets and in-depth investigation related to the subject was considered. For analysis of the marketing strategies of Reliance Industries (Petroleum & Oil Company) in enhancing Its petroleum business & establishing as A global-level petroleum company, this research paper is based on the exploratory investigation related strategies which depend on the data received and sourced from various libraries books, reliable diaries, journals, different sorts of magazines, pertinent books, topic-pertinent articles, reports through media, Etc.

4. DISCUSSION

Reliance Industries Limited as compared with different major six corporations in India: Reliance Industries Limited, Indian Oil Corporation Limited, Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited, Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited, Essar Oil Limited (NAYARA Energy Limited) Mangalore Refinery, Chennai Petro & Petrochemicals Limited, Bharat Oman Refineries Limited.

It is clear that in all the areas like market capital, sales turnover, earnings, etc., reliance features an extremely high position with an interesting distinction in their various values. Whereas we tend to analyses the competition, we can determine that Reliance industries possess a dominance over the market, and it is very tough for the competitors to return over the Reliance industries' position. the fact, corporate profit is vital for Reliance industries to keep up it's standing with additional promoting strategies.

5. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Each character may deliver you individual outcomes; however, it does not imply that the equal consequences belong to the complete population. As a researcher, I will not always be able to undergo all of the resources. I can't acquire all the statistics I wanted for my research in view that it will take a number of times. Because of it, my work won't cover every aspect. Often time limits are the motive why my studies and researches may not be complete. When I get a task, I have a limited amount of time to do it. Sometimes we, as a researcher want a few gadgets or additional software to conduct the researches.

This is probably trouble considering the fact that we don't always have the sum we need. Along with it, there are unique ways to collect information: interviews, surveys, questionnaires, etc. The way we collect records might be a real limitation since the solutions and the outcomes vary. When researchers find some new information, we use a particular research technique. Different techniques supply us with various opportunities. Quality of the datum we get frequently relies upon on the technique we choose.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Reliance Industries Limited is India's biggest non-public sector enterprise on all major financial parameters. Reliance Industries Limited's activities include hydrocarbon exploration and production, petroleum refining and promoting, petrochemicals and retailing. The petrochemicals segment consists of the production and advertising processes of petrochemical products. The oil and gasoline segment consist of exploration, development, and production of crude oil, rock oil, and natural fuel.

Saudi Aramco, the world's biggest oil exporter, is in talks with Reliance Industries limited and different Indian organizations for making a huge investment in petrochemicals and refinery projects occurring in the country, India. Saudi Aramco CEO Amin Al-Nasser stated that Reliance Industries limited remains to be a high-standard corporation for funding in India and Aramco is intended to work as a partner with Reliance Industries Limited.

India is a funding priority for Saudi Aramco, as there is lots of growth potential. Saudi Aramco is interested in additional investments in India's Reliance Industries Limited. Reliance operates refineries at Jamnagar with a total potential of 68.2 million tonnes consistent with annum. Reliance Industries Limited is planning to extend its 'only-for-exports' special economic zone refining capacity to simply over 41 million tons from present-day 35.2 million tonnes. Reliance Industries Limited is presently focusing on increasing its petrochemicals by knowing the fact that crude oil is the fundamental raw material and component for producing petrochemicals. Saudi Arabia, on the alternative hand, is eager to get a foothold within the world's fastest-growing fuel market, India to get a captive consumer base for the crude oil consumption which Aramco produces.

Saudi Aramco, the world's largest oil corporates, and its companion Abu Dhabi National Oil Co (ADNOC) have taken up a 50 percent stake in a planned 44-billion-dollars refinery in Maharashtra. Aramco and ADNOC will together maintain 50 percentage stake-holdings in the 60 million tons per annum refinery and adjacent 18 MTPA petrochemical differentiated planned to be constructed at Ratnagiri district of Maharashtra with the aid of 2025.

Like other major producers, Saudi Aramco and Abu Dhabi National Oil Co (ADNOC) are seeking to lock in clients inside the world's third-largest oil purchaser via their investment plans. That why a very bright and promising future opportunity is waiting in line for Reliance Industries limited and will have collectively encouraging Reliance Industries limited for becoming a proven world-class petroleum-based company.

REFERENCES

1. Press Information Bureau (2013), Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas, Government of India, Crude oil price on Indian Basket
2. <https://www.motilaloswal.com>
3. Pride, W. M. and Ferrel, O. C. (1993). *Marketing: Study Guide*. Houghton- Mifflin School
4. <http://petroleum.nic.in>
5. Dr. T. Srinivasan, (2015), A Study on Consumer Preferences of Petroleum Retail Outlets. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 17, Issue 2. Ver. II (Feb. 2015), PP 35-40
6. <https://www.firstpost.com>
7. Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas Government of Economics and Statistics Division New Delhi
8. Dr. K. Soundarapandiyam, Dr. M. Ganesh, (2017), An Analytical View of Crude Oil Prices and Its Impact on Indian Economy, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668 PP 23-28
9. Ferrell, O., Hartline, M., Lucas, G., Luck, D. (1998). "Marketing Strategy". Orlando, FL: Dryden Press.
10. Acharya, Shankar. 2004. "India's Growth Prospects Revisited," *Economic and Political Weekly* (Oct. 9).
11. Ahluwalia, Monteck. 2002. "Economic Reforms in India Since 1991: Has Gradualism Worked?" *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, vol 16, no. 3:67-88.
12. Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas Government of Economics and Statistics Division New Delhi
13. Dr. K. Soundarapandiyam, Dr. M. Ganesh, (2017), An Analytical View of Crude Oil Prices and Its Impact on Indian Economy, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668 PP 23-28
14. Baier, S. L., G. P. Dwyer Jr., and R. Tamura. 2006. "How Important are Capital and Total Factor Productivity for Economic Growth?" *Economic Inquiry*, 44(1): 23 - 49.
15. Banga, Rashmi, and Bishwananth Gopldar. 2004. "Contribution of Services to Output Growth and Productivity In Indian Manufacturing: Pre And Post Reforms," working paper 139, ICRIER
16. National Sample Survey Organization. 1997. *Employment and Unemployment Situation in India, 1993-1994*. NSS 50th Round, Report No. 409 (New Delhi: Government of India).
17. Saha, V., A. Kar and T. Baskaran. 2004. "Contribution of Informal Sector and Informal Employment in Indian Economy." Paper presented at 7th Meeting of the Expert Group On Informal Sector Statistics New Delhi (February).
18. Radhakrishna, R (2002). *Agricultural Growth, Employment and Poverty: A Policy Perspective*. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 37 (3).
19. Ghosh, Debosree & Parida, Pratap. (2015). *Air Pollution and India: Current Scenario*. *International Journal of Current Research*.
20. Bhattacharya, Kaushik and Bhattacharya , Indranil (2005), Impact of Increase in Oil Prices on Inflation and Output in India", *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol.36, No.51, pp 4735-4741.
21. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, *OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2011–2020*. Ch. 3 (Rome: FAO, 2011). Rana, B.S., Kumar, R., Tiwari, R., Kumar, R., Joshi, R.K., Garg, M.O., Sinha, A.K., 2013. Transportation fuels from co-processing of waste vegetable oil and gas oil mixtures. *Biomass Bioenergy*. 56, 43-52.
22. Rahman, K.M.; Fahimi, B.; Suresh, G.; Rajarathnam, A.V.; Ehsani, M., "Advantages of switched reluctance motor applications to EV and HEV: design and control issues", *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, Vol. 36, Issue 1, Jan.-Feb. 2000, pp. 111 – 121.
23. Messagie, M.; Boureima, F.-S.; Coosemans, T.; Macharis, C.; Van Mierlo, V. A Range-Based Vehicle Life Cycle Assessment Incorporating Variability in the Environmental Assessment of Different Vehicle Technologies and Fuels. *Energies* 2014, 7, 1467–1482.

24. Hoofman, N.; Oliveira, L.; Messagie, M.; Coosemans, T.; Van Mierlo, J. Environmental Analysis of Petrol, Diesel and Electric Passenger Cars in a Belgian Urban Setting. *Energies* 2016, 9, 84
25. Akansha. S.J, Nitish S.P (2015), Crude oil prices and its impact on Indian economy, *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 3(20): 562-572

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